

Appendix A Literature review process

We started with an initial pool of 271 papers. We then filtered this set by selecting papers with the keywords “dashboard”, “peer”, “reference”, or “social” in their titles or abstracts, reducing the list to 123 papers. Next, we refined the selection by reviewing the abstracts to focus on studies that (1) present a LAD solution, (2) are student-oriented, and (3) incorporate a social comparison feature, narrowing the scope to 33 relevant papers. We further expanded this set by including relevant papers reviewed by [1] (specifically LADs with a social feedback component) and [2] (specifically student-facing LADs that provide feedback on learning progress), bringing the total to 54 papers. To ensure alignment with our study’s focus, we applied additional criteria by thoroughly reading each paper, retaining only those that (1) target higher education, (2) provide feedback on students’ study progress, activity, or performance, (3) utilize course activity data from a Learning Management System (LMS), a Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), or tool data, (4) involve explicit student participation in the LAD evaluation, and (5) explicitly report social frame (=peer comparison) features. The final set consisted of 23 papers, offering a comparative view across multiple dimensions. The aforementioned literature review process is summarized in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Overview of the search and selection procedures.

Appendix B Design cycle 1: visualizations questionnaire

Please select a preferred visualization from the given options for each activity type (Q1-Q8).

Fig. 2: Q1: Exercise sessions

Fig. 3: Q2: Home Assignments

Fig. 4: Q3: Modeling activity

Fig. 5: Q4: Number of online exercise sessions

Fig. 6: Q5: Score on online exercise sessions

Fig. 7: Q6: Number of online quizzes

Fig. 8: Q7: Score on online quizzes

Fig. 9: Q8: Practice test score

Please rank the sources for visualizations according to your preferences for their appearance on the LAD page (Q9).

Fig. 10: Q9: Ranking of visualizations

Appendix C Design cycle 1: post-course questionnaire

1. Please indicate to what extent you agree/disagree with the statements below based on your experience of using the dashboard. In case the statement is irrelevant (e.g., you did not use the peer version of the dashboard), choose the "Not relevant" option.

[More Details](#)

Fig. 11: Q1

2. Based on your experience using the dashboard, please indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the statements below.

[More Details](#)

Fig. 12: Q2

Appendix D Historical performance

Table 1: Historical performance based on the final grade (including retakes). Statistical significance is test using Mann–Whitney U test.

Academic year	MInfM avg. grade	MBISE avg. grade	Significantly different?
AY 2017-2018	12.1	13.3	No
AY 2018-2019	11.3	13.7	Yes
AY 2019-2020	11.8	14.0	Yes
AY 2020-2021	11.7	13.1	Yes
AY 2021-2022	10.7	12.1	Yes
AY 2022-2023	9.9	12.5	Yes

Appendix E Design cycle 2: Questionnaire

1. Below are several examples of how AI could enhance the learning analytics dashboard. Please **rank these features from most useful (1) to least useful (4)** for supporting your learning in this course.

Fig. 13: Q1

2. You ranked one of the options as the most useful. Please **explain why you consider this type of AI support especially valuable**.
For example, you could mention what kind of learning situation it can help with, what makes it stand out, or how it can support your study goals.

48
Responses

Latest Responses

"Study recommender can provide me with informed recommendatio...
"This would make it easier to choose a program. This would make it...
"Data summarizer is especially valuable because I for example use ...

Fig. 14: Q2

3. Please briefly comment on the **other options you did not rank as your top choice** — do you still find them valuable, or not really relevant for your learning, and why?
For each option not ranked as the first one, you could mention when you would use it, what it helps you achieve, or why it doesn't fit your needs.

45
Responses

Latest Responses

"Data summarizar is also valuable, as it can visualize my learning pr...
"Knowledge mastery map is also as good as the data summarizer b...

Fig. 15: Q3

4. When viewing your learning analytics (e.g., quiz scores, exercise results, or participation), **what kind of comparison** would you find most useful to see in charts or summaries?

Fig. 16: Q4

5. Learning analytics information (e.g., progress summaries, predictions, or recommendations) could be shared with you at different times. **How often would you like to be notified or prompted (e.g. via e-mail, app) about updates to your learning analytics data?**

Fig. 17: Q5

References

1. I. Jivet, M. Scheffel, M. Specht, and H. Drachsler, "License to evaluate: Preparing learning analytics dashboards for educational practice," in *Proceedings of the 8th international conference on learning analytics and knowledge*, pp. 31–40, 2018.
2. W. Matcha, D. Gašević, A. Pardo, *et al.*, "A systematic review of empirical studies on learning analytics dashboards: A self-regulated learning perspective," *IEEE transactions on learning technologies*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 226–245, 2019.